

A case report of a giant epididymal cyst

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Abstract

Epididymal cyst is commonly seen in middle aged. The pathogenesis of epididymal cyst is still unclear. Small epididymal cyst are asymptomatic but are detected on ultrasound examination of scrotum. Giant epididymal cyst is even rarer in adults and children. We present the case of a 25 year old man with giant mass in right scrotum, which was clinically diagnosed as a right epididymal cyst. An ultrasound of the scrotum revealed images supporting a giant epididymal cyst. Intraoperatively, a giant epididymal cyst was observed, for which the patient underwent its excision. Postoperatively, the patient is doing well of follow-up.

Keywords: Giant Epididymal Cyst; Ultrasound; Surgical excision; Spermatocele; Asymptomatic

1. Introduction

Epididymal cyst or spermatocele is a fluid-filled sac arising from epididymis containing serous fluid (1). It commonly affects middle-aged males (2). An asymptomatic, bilateral, and multilocular giant epididymal cyst is extremely rare, and only a few cases have been reported until today (3,4). Surgery is indicated if the cysts are larger than 10 mm or 1 cm. (5). Here, we present a rare case report of giant epididymal cyst in a middle-aged man.

2. Case report

A 25-year-old man visited the Hospital with complaint of swelling of right scrotal contents. Interrogation reveals that this was evolving for over 3 years. He had no history of fever, pain or difficulty of urination. Physical examination revealed a giant mass in right scrotum without inguinal hernia, the transillumination test was positive. An ultrasound of the bursae was performed and found large liquid effusion in the right scrotum related to an epididymal cyst. Surgical excision revealed a giant cyst measuring 40 cm in its largest axis (A), with 1500 ml of fluid aspirated from the cyst, which was negative in bacterial culture. Histological examination revealed inflammatory changes. The etiology and pathogenesis of this disease is discussed. There has been no evidence of recurrence after one year.

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Figure 1 Image of Giant Epididymal cyst

3. Discussion

Epididymal cyst is a benign fluid-filled sac in the testicles. There is not yet consensus regarding the pathogenesis of epididymal cyst, and to date various theories may be encountered within the literature (6). The etiology of the common form of cystic disease of the epididymis would appear to be obscure according to current teaching(7).

Most often, the cyst is incidentally discovered but can manifest as scrotal discomfort or, in some cases, more acute pain suggestive of torsion. On clinical examination, there is an epididymal swelling located above a normal testicle, presenting as a hard and smooth mass, often transilluminable. However, sometimes the examination is hindered by reactive hydrocele. Diagnostic confirmation is provided by ultrasound, which shows a well-defined, rounded, anechoic image embedded in the epididymis, typically allowing differentiation from other benign tumors (mesothelioma, leiomyoma...) and malignant tumors (mesenchymal, epithelial...)(8). The standard treatment for an epididymal cyst is cystectomy through a scrotal incision.

4. Conclusion

Surgical treatment is the treatment of choice for symptomatic and large-sized epididymal cysts, leading the high patient satisfaction. The diagnosis of this condition is optimally established through clinical examination and ultrasound, which can help identify the origin and appearance of the mass.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

The present research work does not contain any studies performed on animals/humans subjects by any of the authors.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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